

B0801

Relative Diffusivity of Partially Saturated GDLs

**Amin Mohammadi (1), Claire McCague (1), Esmail N. Alvar (2), Pascal Kim (2),
Majid Bahrami* (1)**

(1) Laboratory for Alternative Energy Conversion (LAEC), School of Mechatronic Systems
Engineering, Simon Fraser University, British Columbia/Canada;

(2) Ballard Power Systems, BC V5J 5J8 Burnaby/Canada;

*Contact corresponding authors: www.EFCF.com/ContactRequest

Abstract

Gas diffusivity in GDLs of PEM fuel cells is significantly affected by water content, as water blocks pores and reduces gas flow. This effect increases at higher current densities due to more water production. However, few studies in the literature have experimentally measured gas diffusivity in partially saturated GDLs, primarily due to the challenges of controlling GDL saturation during measurement. Existing studies reported an exponential decay in diffusivity as saturation increases. However, the rate of diffusivity reduction differs between studies. One study suggests that the higher reduction in diffusivity observed in other papers is due to the GDL stacking to increase resistance to gas flow which causes the formation of a thin film of water at the interface between the stacked GDLs during the saturation process, obstructing the diffusion pathway and leading to inaccurate measurements.

In this study, we have developed a new ex-situ method using the symmetrical modified Loschmidt cell to measure gas diffusivity in partially saturated GDLs. This method ensures no water film between the layers, providing more accurate diffusivity measurements. The technique has been applied to two commercially available GDL samples (Toray and AvCarb) under different saturation levels (defined as water volume over the total pore volume of the GDL). Our results indicate a significant decline in relative gas diffusivity as the saturation level increases. Moreover, all GDLs show very low relative diffusivity at saturation levels above 0.3, explaining the deterioration in fuel cell performance under flooding conditions.

1. Introduction

For the widespread adoption of fuel cells in the transportation sector, reducing the overall fuel cell system cost is essential [1]. One effective approach to achieving this is by increasing the power density of the cell, thereby producing more power per unit volume and potentially lowering material and manufacturing costs. However, operating at higher current densities increases water production within the cell. This excess water can result in flooding, particularly in the gas diffusion layer (GDL), where accumulated liquid water blocks the pores. Such flooding reduces the effective gas diffusivity in the GDL, hindering the delivery of reactants to the catalyst layer and ultimately impairing cell performance. Therefore, understanding how water saturation impacts gas diffusivity in the GDL is critical for optimizing fuel cell operation under high power density conditions.

Although several techniques have been developed to measure gas diffusivity in GDLs, including the galvanic cell oxygen sensor [2], modified Loschmidt cell [3], diffusion bridge [4], limiting current method [5], and electrochemical diffusimetry [6], experimental data on the effect of water saturation remains limited. This gap is primarily due to the challenges associated with controlling and maintaining consistent saturation levels during measurement. Among the available studies, most experimental data were obtained using either the limiting current method or the galvanic cell oxygen sensor.

In the limiting current approach, the cell is operated at its highest current density, and this is correlated to gas diffusivity by applying Faraday's and Fick's laws. One of the limitations of this method lies in the fact that water is continuously produced during cell operation, which changes the saturation level of the GDL over time. To mitigate this, Hwang et al. [7] proposed the use of a hydrogen pump cell in which oxygen is excluded from the cathode side. This modification prevents water production during the test, thereby allowing the initial saturation level of the GDL to remain more stable. They reported that treating GDLs with PTFE enhanced the diffusivity of the GDL under partial saturation conditions.

In the galvanic cell setup, the GDL is mounted in a holder that exposes one side to ambient air, while the opposite side is sealed within a chamber where oxygen is electrochemically consumed. The generated current in this arrangement reflects the oxygen concentration inside the chamber, providing a means to estimate gas diffusivity. However, a key limitation of this method is the need for a relatively thick GDL stack to generate a measurable resistance to gas flow. For instance, Iwasaki et al. [8] employed a stack comprising 131 GDL layers to obtain sufficient signal strength for diffusivity evaluation.

Despite both methods demonstrating a general trend of decreasing diffusivity with increasing saturation, the magnitude of the reduction varies. Hwang et al. [7] suggested that the larger reduction seen in the galvanic cell measurements [9] could stem from additional water accumulation between stacked layers.

The primary objective of this study is to quantify the impact of water saturation on the effective gas diffusivity in GDLs, which is a critical factor in the performance of polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs). To achieve this, a new method based on a symmetrical modified Loschmidt cell (SMLC) is introduced. SMLC is a well-established method for measuring gas-phase diffusivity in porous media under dry conditions. To account for the effect of water saturation, the following key modifications are incorporated to the traditional Loschmidt design: (i) the number of GDL layers used in the stack is minimized, (ii) humidified gases are introduced to suppress evaporation within the GDL during testing, and (iii) a robust technique for estimating the saturation level in the GDL is developed.

Unlike the limiting current approach, which requires post-processing to isolate the GDL's contribution from the other cell components, the present method enables a direct measurement of GDL diffusivity. In contrast to the galvanic cell method, which necessitates a large stack of layers to obtain a measurable signal, our setup requires, at most, two layers.

This prevents interfacial water buildup, a common artifact in stacked measurements. The methodology is applied to two different commercial GDLs to investigate their gas transport behavior under different saturation conditions.

2. Experiments/Calculations/Simulations

2.1. Diffusivity Measurement of Dry GDLs

The SMLC apparatus consists of two gas chambers, which are separated by a sliding gate valve where the GDL is installed. The physical setup and the schematic representation of the SMLC are shown in Fig. 1a and Fig. 1b, respectively.

Fig. 1 a) Symmetrical modified Loschmidt cell (SMLC) test stage b) Schematic of SMLC measurement setup c) Prepared GDL stack in Kapton gasket.

To evaluate the diffusivity of a GDL using the SMLC, two sets of measurements must be conducted, one with the GDL mounted and one without. The difference between these measurements is directly related to the diffusive resistance of the GDL. This section outlines the procedure for measuring the diffusivity of a dry GDL.

The procedure begins with temperature stabilization of the test stage, which is achieved using a heating-cooling circulator capable of maintaining the temperature within ± 0.1 °C. Following this, the oxygen sensor is calibrated to account for variables such as temperature shifts, humidity changes, and long-term sensor degradation.

The GDL stack is then prepared. GDL samples with a diameter of $1\frac{3}{4}$ inches are cut from larger GDL sheets. These samples are then enclosed between Kapton gaskets, which serve to seal the edges, maintain the alignment of the layers, and prevent relative movement between adjacent layers during the experiment, as shown in Fig. 1c. Rather than using a single GDL layer, a multi-layer stack is used to enhance the overall resistance to gas flow. This increased resistance is essential for aligning the oxygen concentration change rate with the response time of the oxygen sensor, thereby minimizing measurement uncertainty. The exact number of layers in the stack is determined based on the diffusivity of the GDL. Samples with higher diffusivity require additional layers to generate a detectable concentration gradient across the stack. Since the diffusivity of a new sample is not known in advance, a trial-and-error method is typically used to identify the optimal number of layers that ensures reliable measurements. In most cases, stacking between six and twelve layers provides sufficient resistance for accurate diffusivity assessment.

After sample preparation, the thickness of the GDL stack is measured using a Darnon micrometer with an accuracy of 0.0001 inches. Once measured, the sample is carefully

placed within the slot of the sliding gate valve. Before any diffusion measurement takes place, the entire system is checked for leakage. This is done by pressurizing the chambers with nitrogen and monitoring the pressure drop over time; a leak rate below 2 psi per hour is considered acceptable [10].

After confirming seal integrity, the gas chambers are purged, nitrogen gas is introduced into the upper chamber, and oxygen is introduced into the lower one. This purging step continues for 10 to 20 minutes, until a stable baseline is reached. The measurement begins when the sliding gate valve is rotated to position the GDL between the two chambers, allowing diffusion to occur due to the established concentration gradient. As oxygen passes through the GDL toward the upper chamber, the concentration change is continuously monitored using a PyroScience oxygen sensor (Model No.: OXB50). Depending on the level of resistance posed by the GDL, the diffusion process is tracked for a duration of approximately 3 to 5 minutes.

Once the concentration data is collected, it is analyzed by fitting the measurements to the analytical solution of Fick's second law. This allows the determination of a pseudo-probe position, defined as the location where the oxygen sensor believes it is located, assuming that the entire cell has a uniform diffusion coefficient. The same measurement protocol is repeated without the GDL present, and a second pseudo-probe position is obtained. The difference between the two provides a quantitative measure of the GDL's diffusive resistance, and the diffusivity of the GDL can be calculated as:

$$D^* = \frac{D_{eff}}{D_b} = \frac{x_s}{2(x_b - x_a) + x_s} \quad (1)$$

where x_a and x_b are the pseudo-probe positions of the two experiments, D_b is binary diffusion of oxygen into nitrogen, D_{eff} is the effective diffusion coefficient of the GDL, and x_s is the GDL thickness.

2.2. Diffusivity Measurement of Partially Saturated GDLs

Saturation in a GDL is defined as the ratio between the volume of water contained within the GDL and the total pore volume available. In this study, the vacuum impregnation technique [7] is used to saturate the GDL.

To investigate gas diffusivity at varying levels of saturation, the GDL is first brought to the highest saturation achievable. Then, by allowing evaporation of water from the saturated GDL prior to mounting it into the sliding gate valve, different saturation levels can be obtained for subsequent measurements.

Conducting a measurement on a partially saturated GDL takes approximately 45 minutes from the moment it is removed from the saturation setup. During this period, water gradually evaporates from the GDL, leading to changes in its saturation level. To mitigate this effect and slow down the evaporation process, two humidifiers (CellKraft models P-10C-1C-2-0-031300-v7 and P-10C-1B-2-0-031200-v9) are integrated into the SMLC setup to humidify the nitrogen and oxygen streams during the purging stage. These devices are configured to deliver at 28 °C and 75% relative humidity (RH). To prevent condensation inside the SMLC apparatus, the SMLC is maintained at a slightly higher temperature of 33 °C, resulting in an internal relative humidity of approximately 56%.

Direct measurement of the GDL's saturation level within the SMLC during operation is not possible. To overcome this limitation, a separate environmental chamber (shown in Fig. 2) is used to replicate the conditions present in the SMLC. In this chamber, a second GDL sample, referred to as the control sample, is placed. This control sample is prepared to have the same initial saturation level as the test sample inside the SMLC, which is referred to as the experimental sample. Since both samples are subjected to identical environmental conditions, they show the same rate of water loss. As a result, by periodically monitoring the

saturation level of the control sample, an accurate estimate of the experimental sample's saturation level can be obtained. The saturation is quantified using the following expression:

$$S = \frac{m_{wet} - m_{dry}}{\rho_{water} \left(\frac{\pi d^2}{4} \delta \right)} \tag{2}$$

In this context, m_{dry} refers to the dry mass of the GDL, while m_{wet} denotes its mass after saturation. The variable ϵ represents the GDL's porosity, ρ_{water} is the density of water, d is the GDL diameter, and δ is its thickness. The porosity values used in this study were determined via the buoyancy method [11].

Once the diffusivity test is complete, the final saturation level of the experimental sample is measured. This value is then compared to the saturation of the control sample to verify that both have experienced equivalent mass loss due to evaporation. As shown in Fig. 3, the comparison confirms that the control sample provides a reliable reference for estimating the saturation level of the GDL under test conditions.

Fig. 2 Humidified chamber with a balance to measure the saturation level of the control sample.

Fig. 3 Saturation level of the experimental and control samples over time. Both samples show the same initial and final concentration levels.

In contrast to measurements under dry conditions, which typically require stacking 6 to 12 GDL layers to achieve sufficient diffusive resistance, saturated samples inherently show higher resistance to gas transport. As a result, depending on the degree of saturation, no more than two GDL layers are necessary for saturated measurements.

For tests conducted at lower saturation levels, two individual GDL layers are first saturated independently and then carefully assembled into a stack. This approach helps prevent the formation of a water film at the interface, which could otherwise result from saturating the stack as a whole. The combined diffusive resistance of the two partially saturated layers is adequate for reliable measurement.

At higher saturation levels, however, the increased resistance caused by the water within the pores allows the use of a single GDL layer. The elevated saturation itself provides sufficient opposition to gas diffusion, eliminating the need for additional layers.

2.3. GDL Samples

This study used two types of carbon paper-based gas diffusion layers, whose characteristics are summarized in Table 1. The first sample is TGP-060, which contains 5% PTFE. The second is a GDL manufactured by AvCarb Material Solutions. None of the GDLs used in this study are coated with a microporous layer (MPL).

Table 1 GDL samples and their properties.

GDL	MPL	PTFE content	Porosity	Thickness [μm]
TGP-060	-	5%	0.778 ± 0.003	215 ± 2
AvCarb substrate	-	Not Specified	0.872 ± 0.002	200 ± 2

3. Results

The diffusivity of the dry GDLs was measured first, and the results for TGP-060 are compared with data in the literature in Fig. 4. Because literature data on the diffusivity of TGP-060 with 5% PTFE are not available, our measurements were validated through comparison with published values for untreated TGP-060. Prior studies [4] indicate that incorporating 5% PTFE into TGP-060 has only a marginal impact on its gas diffusivity in dry conditions, which justifies this approach for validation. It's also important to note that untreated TGP-060 was not commercially accessible, prompting the use of the 5% PTFE-treated version in our experiments. As shown in Fig. 4, the diffusivity values obtained from the modified Loschmidt cell setup, along with a CO₂ sensor, align with the uncertainty bounds of our current measurements. In contrast, results from two other experimental techniques report lower diffusivity values.

Fig. 4 Comparing the dry diffusivity of TGP-060 with 5% PTFE with data in the literature on TGP-060 without PTFE treatment. The literature data are measured using different methods, including the limiting current method [7], modified Loschmidt cell [3], electrochemical diffusimetry [6], and CO₂ diffusion [12].

The diffusivity of the TGP-060 with 5% PTFE is compared with AvCarb substrate in Fig. 5. As shown, the diffusivity of the AvCarb substrate is higher than the TGP-060, which was expected due to its higher porosity (see Table 1).

Fig. 5 Comparing the measured diffusivity of TGP-060 with 5% PTFE and AvCarb substrate.

The measurement procedure for partially saturated GDLs followed the approach outlined in Section 2.2. The resulting relative diffusivity values for TGP-060 with 5% PTFE across a range of saturation levels are presented in Fig. 6, alongside previously published data for TGP-060 and TGP-120 without PTFE. It is important to highlight that Hori et al. [9] reported effective diffusivity values (D_{eff}), which were converted into relative diffusivity (D^*) by normalizing with the binary diffusion coefficient of oxygen in air at 25°C and atmospheric pressure (2.07×10^{-5} m²/s) [13]. Notably, their reported dry relative diffusivity values were

significantly higher than those obtained through the SMLC method and other data available in the literature.

All three data sets in Fig. 6 show a consistent trend of exponential decline in diffusivity as water saturation increases, though the magnitude of reduction varies. At low saturation levels, the limiting current method [7] yields higher diffusivity values than those measured in this study or by the galvanic cell technique [9]. Hwang et al. [7] proposed that the comparatively lower diffusivity observed using the galvanic cell setup resulted from water film formation between stacked GDL layers. However, the present measurements, which were conducted with individual layers saturated separately to prevent such interfacial films, still indicate lower diffusivity values than those obtained via the limiting current approach.

One plausible explanation for this discrepancy is the variation in the type of GDL used. While this study and the galvanic cell method were both applied to TGP-060, the limiting current method used TGP-120. Although these two GDLs share similar microstructural features, previous studies [14] have shown differences in their porosity distributions, which could influence gas transport properties under partially saturated conditions.

Another factor potentially contributing to the lower diffusivity reported by the galvanic cell method relates to asymmetric evaporation conditions across the GDL stack. In that configuration [9], one side of the stack was exposed to ambient air, promoting evaporation, while the opposite side was enclosed, limiting moisture loss. This imbalance likely caused non-uniform water content within the stack, with layers near the enclosed side remaining more saturated, thereby reducing the overall diffusivity.

In all three data sets presented in Fig. 6, GDL saturation was established via the vacuum impregnation method. This involved initially saturating the GDL to its maximum capacity and then partially drying it through controlled exposure to ambient air to achieve specific saturation levels. This method predominantly removes water near the external surfaces of the GDL, while the interior regions typically retain high saturation. In contrast, during actual fuel cell operation, water distribution is governed by factors such as capillary pressure and condensation, which may lead to a more complex internal saturation profile. Consequently, while the current ex-situ measurements offer valuable insights, they may not fully capture the water distribution and corresponding gas diffusivity behavior of GDLs under in-situ conditions. Due to experimental limitations, accurately replicating the internal water configuration found in operating fuel cells remains a challenge in ex-situ testing.

Fig. 6 Comparing the measured diffusivity for TGP-060 with 5% PTFE under different saturation levels with literature data, collected with the galvanic cell method (red circles) [9] and the limiting current method (green squares) [7].

The diffusivity behavior of the two GDLs under varying levels of saturation is compared in Fig. 7. As saturation increases from 0.1 to 0.3, a marked decline in diffusivity is observed across both GDLs, highlighting the significant impact of even moderate water content on gas transport. Beyond a saturation threshold of approximately 0.3, the diffusivity values of the GDLs converge, indicating minimal variation between different types. Within this high-saturation regime, diffusivity approaches negligible levels. This suggests that at elevated saturation levels, water accumulation becomes the primary barrier to gas diffusion, effectively overshadowing the influence of structural differences among the GDL substrates.

Fig. 7 Relative diffusivity of partially saturated GDLs. Saturation decreases diffusivity significantly, and at saturation levels above 0.3, all GDLs show a similar diffusivity

Conclusion

A new ex-situ method is proposed to measure the effect of water saturation on gas diffusivity in GDLs, based on the symmetrical modified Loschmidt cell. The diffusivity of two GDLs was measured and compared across varying saturation levels. Results show that diffusivity decreases exponentially with increasing saturation. At low saturation levels, the decrease is significant, and beyond a saturation level of 0.3, the diffusivity of both GDLs approaches zero.

References

- [1] Çabukoglu, Emir, Gil Georges, Lukas Küng, Giacomo Pareschi, and Konstantinos Boulouchos. "Fuel cell electric vehicles: An option to decarbonize heavy-duty transport? Results from a Swiss case-study." *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment* 70 (2019): 35-48.
- [2] Utaka, Yoshio, Yutaka Tasaki, Shixue Wang, Toru Ishiji, and Shoich Uchikoshi. "Method of measuring oxygen diffusivity in microporous media." *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer* 52, no. 15-16 (2009): 3685-3692.
- [3] Unsworth, Grant, Lu Dong, and Xianguo Li. "Improved experimental method for measuring gas diffusivity through thin porous media." *AIChE Journal* 59, no. 4 (2013): 1409-1419.
- [4] Mangal, Prafful, Lalit M. Pant, Nicholas Carrigy, Mark Dumontier, Valentin Zingan, Sushanta Mitra, and Marc Secanell. "Experimental study of mass transport in PEMFCs: Through plane permeability and molecular diffusivity in GDLs." *Electrochimica acta* 167 (2015): 160-171.

- [5] Baker, Daniel R., David A. Caulk, Kenneth C. Neyerlin, and Michael W. Murphy. "Measurement of oxygen transport resistance in PEM fuel cells by limiting current methods." *Journal of The Electrochemical Society* 156, no. 9 (2009): B991.
- [6] Kramer, Denis, Stefan A. Freunberger, Reto Flückiger, Ingo A. Schneider, Alexander Wokaun, Felix N. Büchi, and Günther G. Scherer. "Electrochemical diffusimetry of fuel cell gas diffusion layers." *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry* 612, no. 1 (2008): 63-77.
- [7] Hwang, G. S., and A. Z. Weber. "Effective-diffusivity measurement of partially-saturated fuel-cell gas-diffusion layers." *Journal of The Electrochemical Society* 159, no. 11 (2012): F683.
- [8] Iwasaki, Daigo, Yoshio Utaka, Yutaka Tasaki, and Shixue Wang. "Oxygen diffusion characteristics of gas diffusion layers with moisture." In International Conference on Nanochannels, Microchannels, and Minichannels, vol. 48345, pp. 1279-1284. 2008.
- [9] Hori, Ryosuke, Ikuyasu Kato, Atsushi Ida, Atsushi Yamamoto, and Yuki Sano. "Measurement Technique of Effective Oxygen Diffusion-Coefficient of Water-Containing Gas Diffusion Layers." *ECS Transactions* 80, no. 8 (2017): 113.
- [10] Waterloo Technical Instruments Inc., "Symmetrical Modified Loschmidt Cell: Operator's Manual." 2017.
- [11] Rashapov, Rinat R., Jonathan Unno, and Jeff T. Gostick. "Characterization of PEMFC gas diffusion layer porosity." *Journal of The Electrochemical Society* 162, no. 6 (2015): F603.
- [12] Yoshimune, Wataru, Satoru Kato, Masahide Inagaki, and Satoshi Yamaguchi. "A simple method to measure through-plane effective gas diffusivity of a gas diffusion layer for polymer electrolyte fuel cells." *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer* 191 (2022): 122887.
- [13] Fuller, Edward N., Paul D. Schettler, and J. Calvin Giddings. "New method for prediction of binary gas-phase diffusion coefficients." *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry* 58, no. 5 (1966): 18-27.
- [14] Fishman, Z., J. Hinebaugh, and A. Bazylak. "Microscale tomography investigations of heterogeneous porosity distributions of PEMFC GDLs." *Journal of the Electrochemical Society* 157, no. 11 (2010): B1643.

Keywords: *Keywords: EFCF2025, H₂, Low-Temp. Fuel Cells & Electrolysers, Gas diffusion layer; Symmetrical modified Loschmidt cell; Gas diffusivity; Partially saturated GDLs*

Remark: *This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International*